

Annotation: The main goal of the new Uzbekist people is " to maintain a just social and political system , to improve human well - being Article 4 " The spiritual , intellectual , physical and mental health of young people a xl o qiji jih a td a nk a m olt o pishig a k o ' m a kl a sh; Providing high - quality education for young people , perfect education for young people in all areas of education Ensuring education , creating conditions for the development of inclusive education in the region " was designated as the task As a result , priority is given to improve the quality of teaching and learning in general pedagogy It is important to understand , integrate the family and work in the pedagogical process of teaching and learning.

Key words: Projecting method, cluster method, speech competence, education.

Аннотация. Реализация этой задачи требует повышения качества образования на основе педагогики сотрудничества, согласно требованиям личностно-ориентированной стратегии образования.

Ключевые слова: метод проекции, кластерный метод, речевая компетентность, образование.

In the students competencies to form directed education technologies in students support competencies formation for education technologies when choosing study science o ' teacher calendar topic in the plan this class for defined support competencies set takes From this after , to be studied necessary was topic and formable competencies account received without the lesson tooth method , method is selected .

An interactive approach. Teachers create a comfortable environment for good organization of the lesson process. Students are allowed to exchange ideas (information). They discuss and resolve the pending issues together. They will find a solution in cooperation to get out of the situation. They demonstrate their knowledge to each other based on the information they have received.

Design method. The design method is a teaching system in which students acquire knowledge, skills, and competences in the process of planning, constructing , and executing practical tasks that are continuously increasing in complexity. carry out projects related to issues . In order for this method to be highly effective, students must have a high level of motivation in completing the project.

Through the projecting method, the following personal competencies are formed in students: team work; diligence; sense of responsibility; self-confidence; teachability; quick thinking; being able to see the progress of the process; ability to observe; foresight; diagnosis; motivation. Critical thinking method Problem-based modular education method. The method of problem-based module education involves practical application of the acquired theoretical knowledge.

This method forms the didactic basis of various models of teaching, and is distinguished by teaching tools and methods of using pedagogical techniques. It represents the division of the educational subject into relatively small parts - modules. Education aimed at the development of the student's personality. A person who engages in social relations and actively participates in social development is called a Person. A person born as an individual becomes a person later. A person's lineage is embodied in the concept of an individual.

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a teaching system in which students acquire knowledge, skills, and competencies in the process of planning, constructing, and executing a practical task of increasing complexity .

Learners perform projects related to large-scale problematic issues (creative, informational, communication , etc.) .

The following personal competencies are formed: teamwork; diligence; sense of responsibility; self-confidence; teachability; quick thinking; being able to see the progress of the process; ability to observe; foresight; diagnosis.

CLUSTER (Cluster-set, connection) - the way to create an information map - the essence of the entire structure

gathering ideas around some key factor to center and define.

helps to freely and openly attract new interrelated ideas on the topic to the thinking process . They get acquainted with the rule of forming a cluster. In the center of the blackboard or a large sheet of paper, write the main word or the name of the topic consisting of 1-2 words. By combining the main word with the words and propositions related to the topic next to it, small circles are written "companions". They are connected with the "main" word using lines. These "satellites" may have "minor satellites".

The recording can continue for the time allotted or until the ideas run out. A (general) sign indicating the importance of category-properties and relationships. Provides integration of information obtained on the basis of isolated symptoms. Develops the skills of systematic thinking, structuring and systematization of information. They formalize the categories in the form of a table. The ideas are categorized according to the data. In the course of work, some names of categories may change. New ones may appear. Presentation of work results .

BBB Schedule - I know/ I want to know/ I have learned. Allows you to search by topic, text, section.

Develops the skills of systematic thinking, structuring, and analysis. They got acquainted with the rule of making a table. In separate small groups, they formalize the schedule.

They answer the questions "What do you know about the topic" and "What do you want to know" (creates a guiding basis for future work). They fill in sections 1 and 2 of the table. They listen to the lecture and study independently. In independent small groups, they fill in the 3rd part of the table.

is used to compare or contrast aspects 2 and 3 and common aspects.

Develops the skills of systematic thinking, comparison, comparison, analysis. They will learn the rules of creating a VENNA diagram. In separate small groups, they construct a Venn diagram and fill in the non-intersecting areas (x). They get into pairs, compare and complete their diagrams . Creates a list of data common to two or three circles at the intersection of circles.

1. You choose whether to use circular or rectangular shapes .

You choose the appearance of the drawing - whether the chain of reasoning is straight or not.

3. Direction indicators define your searches: your direction from the initial position to the search.

Self-education is a conscious activity by a person aimed at maximally realizing it as a person. Based on the activation of self-control mechanisms, it assumes the existence of clearly realized goals, ideals , and personal meanings. It is inextricably linked not only to the strengthening of education, but also to the development of the process of personality formation. Necessary components of self-education are self-analysis, self-reporting and self-management of personal development. Self-discipline techniques include self-discipline, self-affirmation, and self-hypnosis. a prerequisite is the presence of true knowledge about oneself, correct appreciation,

self-awareness. Self-education is determined by a number of subjective and objective reasons: the desire to be better, society's requirements for citizens, their information and qualities; Pedagogical influences affecting the student during education and training. Under the influence of these reasons, internal prerequisites for self-education are created, needs, views and beliefs are formed, life ideals and goals are defined or formed. Based on the activation of self-control mechanisms, self-education presupposes the existence of clearly accepted goals and personal meanings. Necessary components of self-education are: reflection of personal development, self-reporting, self-management. Self-discipline techniques include: satisfaction, self-esteem, self-hypnosis, self-reliance, and self-discipline. . The importance of self-improvement in personality formation is recognized by many modern pedagogical and psychological science leaders. AGKovalev's research provided justification for the essence of the processes of self-management and self-improvement. In the works of VG Kutsenko, AA Bodalev and other scientists, the interdependence of raising children and self-education, the method of organizing the process of self-education are considered. In the works of PM Yakobson, the problem of self-education of emotions, psychological features of self-control in the field of emotions are analyzed. Theories, including basic concepts, description of motives, goals, tasks, tools, methods of self-education and improvement, factors affecting the development of these processes P. Ya. Aret, AG Kovalev, LI Ruvinsky, II Chesnokova, SM. Kovalev. In the concept of "self-education", pedagogy describes the inner spiritual world of a person, his ability to develop independently. External factors - education - these are only the conditions, their awakening, the means of their implementation. Therefore, philosophers, teachers, psychologists claim that the driving forces of its development lie in its heart. In the process of education, it is necessary to encourage the teenager to educate himself.

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